

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Power of the unconscious mind - paediatrics & Child Health

Dr. Angela Wilson*

*Achievers Resources, Brisbane City, Australia

Summary: This talk aims to bring accurate thinking in solving paediatrics & child health issues from the root causes at different levels.

Prevention of genetic diseases, problematic mental health issues at a later stage, including depression at middle age starting from at least 12 months prior to preconception. A holistic approach can minimise the risk of losing control after birth, from the conscious, subconscious, and unconscious mind, to the physical body.

It ensures easy parenting and a positive parent-child relationship if children have autism, bipolar disorder, learning disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, attention-deficit disorder (add), schizophrenia, various genetic diseases.

From my research and clinic experience with children who suffer from the problems as mentioned above, the recovery process can be very slow if parents have unsolved emotional and mental health that can connect with up to four generations.

Helping to fix the root causes from parents can bring a miracle solving children's health issues. The result is so apparent if parents are very cooperative comparing those who are not. The power of the unconscious mind can enhance the recovery process and strengthen the child-parent positive relationship and boost the immunity of both during Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: The unconscious mind

**Presenting Author*

Mind power lady, Dr Angela Wilson is known as the authority of the largely inaccessible unconscious mind. She is covid-19 mind matrix specialist and holistic health educator, certified training provider, international speaker, author, and more. Dr Angela Wilson (Ph.D.), initiated her serious research on physical, emotional, and mental health through first-hand personal experiments on a daily basis at the age of six. It led her hands truly on what humanity is looking for but afraid most of us to find, benefiting from her paediatrician father with 11 generations heritage of Chinese herbal medicine practice; the 22nd generation on energy healing; academic study; holistic qualifications; rich clinical experience; and unstoppable cross-disciplinary testing by risking her life researching how human mind connects with physical world, metaphysical world, quantum physics, etc. theory and effects business, career and personal life human mind connects with physical world, metaphysical world, quantum physics, etc. theory and effects business, career and personal life human mind connects with physical world, metaphysical world, quantum physics, etc. theory and effects business, career and personal life.
